

Analysis of Elastic Anisotropy in CFRP Laminate Beam

H. C. Kim¹⁾, Y. J. Yum²⁾

- 1) Physics Department, Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology, P.O. Box 150, Chongyangni, Seoul, Korea
- 2) Mechanical Engineering Department, Ulsan Institute of Technology, Ulsan, Korea

ABSTRACT

Elastic anisotropy in carbon fibre/epoxy composites has been analysed theoretically with the flat wise specimen of lamina, two layer and multilayer laminates. The modulus measurements of unidirectional (0°) and (90°) lamina was shown to be $(E_t)_{0^\circ} = 1.31(E_c)_{0^\circ}$ and $(E_t)_{90^\circ} = 0.93(E_c)_{90^\circ}$ respectively. Theoretical estimation of the neutral axis in the (0°) and (90°) lamina, (0°/90°) and (90°/0°) of two layered, and (0°/90°/90°/0°), (90°/0°/0°/90°), (0°/90° .../0°/90°) of multi-layered laminates has been made. Experimental determination of the neutral axis was made from the modulus measurements. The comparison was made between these two results and the percentage deviation of h_t/h was found to be less than 3% for the laminate with (0°) lamina at the compression side. However, substantial deviation was observed in the laminate with (90°) lamina at the compression side.

NOMENCLATURE

E : modulus
 E_t : tensile modulus
 E_c : compressive modulus
F : force
h : beam thickness
 h_t : height of tensile zone
 h_c : height of compressive zone
N : neutral axis
 σ : normal stress
 ϵ : normal strain
 θ : angle
 ρ : radius of curvature

INTRODUCTION

The advantage of composite lamina over conventional materials is that the directional dependence of strength and stiffness of material can be controlled to match the loading direction of structure, reducing its inherent anisotropy of constituent lamina.

The estimation of neutral axis is an important design consideration to the

structural engineer because composites are frequently used in flexural mode. Generally the neutral axis in anisotropic material is not located at the middle of symmetry, unlike in the isotropic material, due to inequality of tension and compression moduli. However, little work has been found in the open literature despite of its serious engineering implication.

The work of Jones (1) has shown that the tensile modulus of unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy composites is 40% greater than compressive modulus while Piggott and Harris (2), by testing unidirectional carbon fibre/polyester reported less rigid in compression than in tension.

In a recent work (3) one of us and his colleague have reported that the decrease of compressive zone with increasing the strain rate during three point flexural tests of unidirectional carbon fibre/epoxy lamina by direct SEM observation of fracture surface.

This work presents the results of experimentally determined location of neutral axes in (0°) and (90°) lamina, $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ)$ of two layered and $(0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(0^\circ/90^\circ/\dots/0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/\dots/90^\circ/0^\circ)$ of multilayered laminates. These results have been compared with a theoretical estimation which is presented in the following.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Fig. 1. Location of Neutral Axis

The locations of neutral axis in bimodulus composite beam during bending is shown in Fig. (1) as dashed line, where h_c and h_t denote the heights of compressive and tensile zones respectively.

Resultant force at any crosssection of a beam for unit depth is

$$\Sigma F_x = \int_{-h_t}^{h_c} \sigma dy = \int_{-h_t}^0 \sigma_t dy + \int_0^{h_c} \sigma_c dy = 0 \quad \text{---- (1)}$$

Eq. (1) will be used in the following section to calculate the locations of neutral axes in the unidirectional laminae, and laminates having various stacking sequences.

Chamis (2) has shown a theoretical analysis regarding the location of neutral axis in the material having different moduli in tension and compression.

Fig. 2. Neutral axis in Unidirectional Lamina

From eq. (1)

$$\Sigma F_x = \int_{-h_t}^0 -\frac{y}{\rho} E_t dy + \int_0^{h_c} -\frac{y}{\rho} E_c dy = 0$$

After integration and simplifying this equation yields to

$$h_c/h_t = \sqrt{E_t/E_c} \quad h_t/h = \sqrt{E_c}/(\sqrt{E_t} + \sqrt{E_c}). \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Two-layered Laminate

The simplest forms of two-layered laminates are (0°/90°) and (90°/0°) laminates and the neutral axes of these laminates are located either in the upper or lower half of the beam thickness respectively depending on the lamina modulus.

- a. In case of $h_t > h_c$

Fig. 3. Neutral axis in Two-layered Laminate, $h_t > h_c$

From eq. (1)

$$F_x = \int_{-h_t}^{-h_t + \frac{h}{2}} -\frac{yE_{1t}}{\rho} dy + \int_{-ht + \frac{h}{2}}^0 -\frac{yE_{2t}}{\rho} dy + \int_0^{h_c} -\frac{yE_{2c}}{\rho} dy = 0$$

Then, the location of neutral axis in terms of ht/h , will be obtained as follows

$$h_t/h = \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad \text{if } \frac{1}{2} < \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} < 1 \quad \text{--- (3)}$$

$$= \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad \text{if } \frac{1}{2} < \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} < 1$$

where

$$a = E_{2t} - E_{2c}$$

$$b = E_{1t} - E_{2t} + 2E_{2c}$$

$$c = -\frac{1}{4}E_{1t} + \frac{1}{4}E_{2t} - E_{2c}$$

If both of the terms $\frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$ and $\frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$ are not in the range between $\frac{1}{2}$ and 1, which means that neutral axis is not located at the upper half of the beam thickness. In this case, eq. (4), for $h_c > h_t$ should be applied.

b. In case of $h_t < h_c$

Fig. 4. Neutral axis in Two-layered Laminate, $h_t < h_c$

From eq. (1)

$$\Sigma F_x = \int_{-h_t}^0 -\frac{yE_{1t}}{\rho} dy + \int_0^{h_c - \frac{h}{2}} -\frac{yE_{1c}}{\rho} dy + \int_{h_c - \frac{h}{2}}^{h_c} -\frac{yE_{2c}}{\rho} dy = 0$$

Then the location of axis is obtained as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_t/h &= \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} & \text{if } 0 < \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} < \frac{1}{2} \\
 &= \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} & \text{if } 0 < \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} < \frac{1}{2}
 \end{aligned}
 \quad \text{---- (4)}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 a &= E_{1t} - E_{1c} \\
 b &= E_{1c} + E_{2c} \\
 c &= -\frac{1}{4} E_{1c} - \frac{3}{4} E_{2c}
 \end{aligned}$$

Multi-layered Laminate

In the arbitrary multi-layered laminates the locations of neutral axis is obtained as follows

Fig. 5. Neutral axis in multi-layered Laminate

Assuming the neutral axis is located at the distance x from the bottom of k-th layer of the beam, and each layer has the same thickness of $\frac{h}{n}$. Then from eq. (1)

$$\Sigma F_x = \int_{-(\frac{k-1}{n} h) - x}^{(\frac{n-k+1}{n} h) - x} \sigma_t dy + \int_0^{(\frac{n-k+1}{n} h) - x} \sigma_c dy = 0 \quad \text{--- (5)}$$

The stress distribution in each layer is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_t^{(1)} &= E_t^{(1)} \varepsilon_t^{(1)} = E_t^{(1)} \left(-\frac{y}{\rho}\right)^{(1)} & -\left(\frac{k-1}{n} h\right) \cdot x \leq y \leq -\left(\frac{k-2}{n} h\right) \cdot x \\
 \sigma_t^{(2)} &= E_t^{(2)} \varepsilon_t^{(2)} = E_t^{(2)} \left(-\frac{y}{\rho}\right)^{(2)} & -\left(\frac{k-2}{n} h\right) \cdot x \leq y \leq -\left(\frac{k-3}{n} h\right) \cdot x \\
 &\vdots & \\
 \sigma_t^{(k)} &= E_t^{(k)} \varepsilon_t^{(k)} = E_t^{(k)} \left(-\frac{y}{\rho}\right)^{(k)} & -x \leq y \leq 0 \\
 \sigma_c^{(k)} &= E_c^{(k)} \varepsilon_c^{(k)} = E_c^{(k)} \left(-\frac{y}{\rho}\right)^{(k)} & 0 \leq y \leq \frac{h}{n} - x \\
 &\vdots & \\
 \sigma_c^{(n)} &= E_c^{(n)} \varepsilon_c^{(n)} = E_c^{(n)} \left(-\frac{y}{\rho}\right)^{(n)} & \left(\frac{n-k}{n} h\right) \cdot x \leq y \leq \left(\frac{n-k+1}{n} h\right) \cdot x
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting these stresses into eq. (5) and integrating, yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \left\{ \frac{h^2}{2} (2(k-m)-1) + \frac{2hx}{n} \right\} E_t^{(m)} + E_t^{(k)} x^2 \\
 = \sum_{l=k+1}^n \left\{ \frac{h^2}{2} (2(l-k)+1) - \frac{2hx}{n} \right\} E_c^{(l)} + E_c^{(k)} \left(\frac{h}{n} - x\right)^2 \quad \text{--- (6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

From these equation, the location of neutral axis in the multi-layered laminate can be obtained as,

$$h_t = \left(\frac{k-1}{n} h\right) + x \quad \text{--- (7)}$$

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimen Preparation

The nominal one ply thickness of prepreg was 0.16mm and to make a laminate of 50% fibre volume fraction, approximately 20 plies of prepreps were necessary to fill the cavity of the matching mould with the plunger fully closed.

The loaded mould was placed in a preheated press, the plattens of which were thermostatically controlled to 170°C. After waiting for the chosen dwelling time (3), the mould was pressed with a pressure of 50 Kg/cm² and left to cure for one hour. After this the mould was postcured with the atmospheric pressure at the same temperature for three hours. After postcuring the mould is removed and allowed to cool before extracting the specimen.

The maximum top surface strain and maximum bottom surface strain were measured by four point bending using two strain gages with the crosshead speed, 0.55 mm/min. For CFRP unidirectional laminae (0°), (90°) and laminates having various stacking sequences of ($0^\circ/90^\circ$), ($90^\circ/0^\circ$), ($0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$), ($90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$), ($0^\circ/90^\circ/\dots/0^\circ/90^\circ$), ($90^\circ/0^\circ/\dots/90^\circ/0^\circ$).

Fig. 7. Bending specimen (a) 4-pt. bending (b) Bending specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile moduli of (0°) and (90°) unidirectional CFRP laminae were experimentally determined as 34.12 GN/m^2 and 8.34 GN/m^2 respectively. The compressive moduli of these laminae were obtained from tensile moduli and the values of E_c/E_t in eq. (2).

$$(E_c)_{0^\circ} = (h_t/h_c)^2 (E_t)_{0^\circ} = (-\epsilon_t/\epsilon_c)^2 (E_t)_{0^\circ} = \left(\frac{1}{1.146}\right) \times 34.12 = 26.0 \text{ GN/m}^2$$

$$(E_c)_{90^\circ} = (h_t/h_c)^2 (E_t)_{90^\circ} = (-\epsilon_t/\epsilon_c)^2 (E_t)_{90^\circ} = \left(\frac{1}{0.965}\right)^2 \times 8.34 = 8.96 \text{ GN/m}^2$$

$$\therefore (E_t)_{0^\circ} = 1.31 (E_c)_{0^\circ}$$

$$(E_t)_{90^\circ} = 0.93 (E_c)_{90^\circ}$$

$E_t/E_c = 1.31$ of (0°) lamina, which is somewhat less than the value of $E_t/E_c = 1.4$ reported by Jones⁽¹⁾, however, this shows an apparent difference between E_t and E_c and result compressive moduli. And it is to be noted that for a (90°) lamina, compressive modulus is 7% greater than tensile modulus.

The theoretical estimation of neutral axis in two layered and multilayered laminates which was presented in the preceding section, and experimentally determined values are compared in Table I, in terms of h_t/h , where h_t denotes the height of tensile zone and h , the thickness of beam.

Stacking Sequence	Experimental h_t/h	Theoretical h_t/h	Deviation of h_t/h (%)
($0^\circ/90^\circ$)	0.612	0.624	1.9
($90^\circ/0^\circ$)	0.439	0.350	20.3
($0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$)	0.458	0.462	0.9
($90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$)	0.425	0.490	15.3
($0^\circ/90^\circ/\dots/0^\circ/90^\circ$)	0.481	0.490	1.9
($90^\circ/0^\circ/\dots/90^\circ/0^\circ$)	0.471	0.457	3.0

Table 1. Comparison of Theoretical and Experimentally determined h_t/h of Laminates.

It is interesting to note that the percentage deviation of h_t/h in the laminate with (0°) lamina at the compression side was shown to be less than 2%, while the laminate with (90°) lamina at the compression tends to show larger deviation 20.3% and 15.3% for $(90^\circ/0^\circ)$ and $(90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminates respectively.

CONCLUSION

CFRP (0°) and (90°) laminae showed a great anisotropy, showing tensile moduli to be 31% greater and 7% less than compressive moduli for (0°) and (90°) laminae respectively. Consequently the location of neutral zone shifts from the geometrical center line according to the ratio of Compressive and tensile modulus.

Theoretical estimation of the neutral axis has been made for unidirectional lamina (0°) , (90°) , two-layered laminates $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ)$ and multilayered laminates $(0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(0^\circ/90^\circ/.../0^\circ/90^\circ)$, $(90^\circ/0^\circ/.../90^\circ/0^\circ)$ with the different moduli in tension and compression. This prediction has been compared with experimental results of laminates having various stacking sequences.

The experimentally determined location of neutral axis in the lamina and laminates are in good agreement with those of theoretically predicted location except $(90^\circ/0^\circ)$ and $(90^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminates, where the (90°) lamina was subjected the compressive load.

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